

A SIMPLE WATER SAMPLES STORAGE TEST FOR WATER ISOTOPE ANALYSIS

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1. INTRODUCTION

In every experimental discipline, reliable data are the foundation of quality research.

The objective: provide quantitative information on the effects of not in glass storing and multi-day usage of Laboratory Reference Material (LRM) sub-sample over the analysis of water stable isotopes.

2. METHODS

3. RESULTS

The black, red and blue lines represent the mean values, the $\pm 1\sigma$, $\pm 2\sigma$, and $\pm 3\sigma$, and the linear regression.

	Intercept	Intercept Error	Coefficient	Coefficient Error	p - MK test
$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ 60 ml bottle	-9.22 (-9.23)	0.01 (0.01)	$3.73 \cdot 10^{-04}$ ($5.14 \cdot 10^{-04}$)	$2.01 \cdot 10^{-04}$ ($2.04 \cdot 10^{-04}$)	0.14 (0.02)
$\delta^2\text{H}$ 60 ml bottle	-59.9	0.1	$-5.14 \cdot 10^{-03}$	$2.44 \cdot 10^{-03}$	0.87
$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ 15 ml bottles	-9.17	0.01	$-2.91 \cdot 10^{-04}$	$1.63 \cdot 10^{-04}$	0.71
$\delta^2\text{H}$ 15 ml bottles	-60.3 (-60.1)	0.2 (0.2)	$4.72 \cdot 10^{-03}$ ($-3.20 \cdot 10^{-03}$)	$3.22 \cdot 10^{-03}$ ($-3.32 \cdot 10^{-03}$)	0.26 (0.62)

In the table the results of σ weighted linear regression and Mann-Kendall tests are reported. In red the results obtained excluding the outliers.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- Only the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of the 60 ml bottle display significant and positive trend, suggesting evaporation due to repeated opening of the bottle.
- The 15 ml HDPE bottles and the $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of the 60 ml bottle did not show significant variation over the study period.
- Short opening time and frequent replacements are simple measures to prevent undesired LRM sub-sample undesired evaporation.

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- The 60 ml HDPE bottle mimics a LRM sub-sample for daily operation.

- Westgard rules [4, 5] were applied for quality control.

- Data out of 2σ from the mean were considered outliers.

- Mann-Kendall test was applied for trends detection.

- No weight changes were detected for the 15 ml bottles.